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40

41 **Availability of data and material**

42 The dataset is available as a separate Stata file.

43 **Code Availability** – Not applicable

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48 **Evolution of Fertiliser Use and its Impact on Maize Productivity in Kenya: Evidence** 49 **from Multiple Surveys**

50 **1. Introduction**

51 The use of fertiliser has always been an important issue in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) (Tully,
52 Hickman, McKenna, Neill and Palm 2016; Ariga and Jayne 2009), engaging both researchers
53 (Vanlauwe, AbdelGadir, Adewopo, Adjei-Nsiah, Ampadu-Boakye and Asare 2017) and policy
54 makers (Berazneva, McBride, Sheahan and Güereña 2018) in designing the best agricultural
55 policies for increasing farm productivity, while balancing the needs of other stakeholders. The
56 population in SSA is rising fast; a substantial increase in food production is required to keep up
57 with the population growth (Godfray, Beddington, Crute, Haddad, Lawrence and Muir 2010;
58 Gregory and George 2011; Tilman, Cassman, Matson, Naylor and Polasky 2002) and malnutrition
59 is increasing (FAO 2009; FAO 2014). To increase food production, the availability and use of
60 agricultural technologies such as improved varieties and fertiliser remain a central focus of
61 agricultural policy in these countries (Jena and Odendo 2014). The promotion of fertiliser
62 especially has become a resounding theme across SSA in the past decades (Ariga and Jayne 2011;
63 Takeshima and Lee 2012), particularly following the first African Fertiliser Summit in Abuja,
64 Nigeria in 2006. However, the question of whether or not farmers' fertiliser adoption patterns are
65 determined by the profitability of fertiliser application has not been paid serious attention. Farmers
66 in general weigh the opportunity cost of investing in fertiliser against the returns that they are likely
67 to obtain (Duflo, Kremer and Robinson 2007). Any uncertainty in returns from cultivation will
68 reduce their tendency to apply fertiliser.

69 Few credible studies have used an experimental set-up to examine the issue of fertiliser uptake.
70 Duflo, Kremer and Robinson (2008) explored the factors leading to the low adoption of fertiliser
71 in Kenya, including lack of information on the availability of inputs at reasonable prices, and
72 farmers' difficulties in saving sufficient money for their purchase. They suggested simple
73 interventions that could substantially increase fertiliser use without affecting the cost, such as
74 offering farmers the option to buy fertiliser at the full market price but with free delivery
75 immediately after the harvest; this would have an effect comparable to a reduction in price. Further,
76 Duflo, Kremer and Robinson (2008) showed that small, time-limited reductions in the cost of

77 fertiliser at harvest time induced substantial increases in fertiliser use, and that these increases were
78 comparable to those induced by much larger price reductions given later in the season. A study in
79 western Kenya by Waithaka, Thornton, Shepherd and Ndiwa (2007) found that the use of chemical
80 fertiliser and manure influenced each other reciprocally, and were positively influenced by
81 household factors such as the education of the household head.

82 Sheahan, Black and Jayne (2013) showed that farmers in Kenya, over time, and in the most
83 productive areas, consistently and steadily moved towards risk-adjusted, economically optimal
84 rates of fertiliser use. According to Matsumoto and Yamano (2009), relatively lower prices for
85 nitrogen-based fertiliser in Kenya played a decisive role in its high uptake for fertilising maize, as
86 compared to Uganda where nitrogen fertiliser prices were much higher.

87 Ariga and Jayne (2011) showed that between 1997 and 2007 there was a 34% increase in
88 smallholders' application of fertiliser per ha in maize cultivation systems, which was led by public
89 investments in support of input-market development, and by fertiliser-subsidy policies in Kenya.
90 Other studies observed that government fertiliser subsidies and government intervention in
91 fertiliser distribution had crowded out private investment in the sector (Makau, Irungu, Nyikal and
92 Kirimi (2016).

93 Faced with an increasing population and the associated demand for food, as well as the rising cost
94 of fertilisers in Kenya, the Kenya Agricultural Research Institute (KARI) started the Fertiliser Use
95 Recommendation Project (FURP) in 1985. Fertiliser trials were conducted at 70 different sites, all
96 of which were representative of different soil types and agroecological zones. The goal of FURP
97 was to design zone- and crop-specific fertiliser-recommendation packages, which were expected
98 to contribute in turn to higher degrees of self-sufficiency in supplying food throughout Kenya
99 (Kenya Agricultural Research Institute 1995). FURP led to fertiliser recommendations for crops
100 such as maize, beans and sorghum in 24 districts (Kibunja, Ndungu-Magiroi, Wamae, Mwangi,
101 Nafuma and Koech 2017). Using data from FURP, Schnier, Recke, Muchena and Muriuki (1996)
102 analysed the variance in crop yields, including maize, in order to estimate the significance of
103 treatment effects. Step-wise multiple regressions using data for individual seasons and the pooled
104 data, i.e. the average over all the seasons, revealed two major risks that farmers faced when
105 optimizing fertiliser use against their net income per ha: firstly, the crop response to fertiliser may

106 be lower than anticipated due to crop diseases, pests or unfavourable seasonal conditions, and
107 secondly, the price of the crop may be lower than anticipated. The first risk can be mitigated by
108 increasing farmers' knowledge about crop pests and diseases, and increasing their farm
109 management skills, the second by guaranteeing crop prices at harvest time. (Schnier and colleagues
110 (1996) did not find any significant correlations between rainfall data, maize yields and fertiliser
111 responses. The total amount of rainfall was not correlated with the response either to the
112 application of nitrogen fertiliser or to maize yields. They also pointed out that rainfall variability
113 constituted a serious constraint when it came to fertiliser recommendations for rain-dependent
114 agricultural systems, since soil moisture is an important determinant of yield. Consequently, they
115 suggested that under certain conditions, such as adversely high risks in terms of rainfall variability,
116 prohibitive input prices, or very low prices for produce, it was advisable not to apply any fertiliser.
117 Following Schnier et al. (1996), Smaling, Nandwa, Prestele, Roetter and Muchena (1992) also
118 used FURP data, and recommended agroecological-specific fertiliser. They also pointed out that
119 farm heterogeneity, in particular soil type, slope and altitude, must be taken into account when
120 recommending fertiliser rates, as the applicability and overall profitability of these depend on farm
121 labour and capital resources.

122 A more recent example of a fertiliser-recommendation project is the Optimizing Fertiliser
123 Recommendations in Africa (OFRA) 2013-2017 project, during which 37 trials were conducted
124 for various crops in four regions of Kenya ([http://africasoilhealth.cabi.org/about-
125 ashc/ashc/ofra/](http://africasoilhealth.cabi.org/about-ashc/ashc/ofra/)). The aim of OFRA was to deliver decision-making tools to farmers that would
126 enable them to choose the appropriate fertiliser type and rate of application for various crops in
127 different agroecological zones, knowledge of which farmers often lack. OFRA found crop
128 responses to fertiliser application to be non-linear, i.e. fertiliser application has a positive effect on
129 crops until a plateau is reached. Like Schnier et al. (1996), Kibunja et al. (2017) also recommended
130 that fertiliser application rates should be based on input and output prices, and depend on access
131 to information about these. The interaction of fertiliser use with other aspects of integrated pest-,
132 disease-, and soil-fertility management practices should also be considered.

133 Research into the efficient use of fertiliser on maize is important to help establish food security in
134 Kenya, where maize is the most common cereal (FAOSTAT 2020b) and the primary staple food,
135 with an average consumption of 76 kg/year, accounting for 30% of calorie intake and 28% of

136 protein intake (FAOSTAT 2020a). Maize production cannot keep up with the growing population,
137 and poor soil fertility is one of the major constraints (Vanlauwe and Giller 2006). Therefore, in
138 order to provide food security in Kenya, especially for the rural poor, the issue of soil fertility in
139 relation to maize production needs to be addressed, and the use of fertiliser plays a major role in
140 this.

141 Kenya has undergone agricultural liberalisation since the mid-1990s, and policies have been
142 introduced that allow private actors into the seed- and fertiliser-sector markets (Wangia, C.,
143 Wangia, S. and De Groote 2004). However, after several years of agricultural liberalisation, the
144 question still remains as to whether the increased participation of the private sector has increased
145 agricultural productivity and brought growth. This study therefore analyses the changes in fertiliser
146 use in the maize sector in Kenya, from the centrally controlled markets in the early 1990s, over
147 the liberalisation period, and afterwards, and the impact of these changes on maize productivity
148 and economic profitability.

149 Against this backdrop, our study has three objectives: firstly, we analyse the changes in fertiliser
150 use in maize cultivation from before until after the opening up of the agricultural sector to the
151 private sector through the liberalisation of input and output markets. We make use of repeated
152 cross-sectional data collected in Kenya at four points in time – in 1992, 2002, 2010 and 2013. The
153 data for 1992 account for the pre-liberalisation period, in which the national government controlled
154 the prices of maize, inputs and fertiliser. The data for 2002 show the scenario immediately after
155 liberalisation, when private participation was allowed, whereas the latter two periods can be
156 considered as ones in which liberalisation of the fertiliser market was well-established. The second
157 objective is to identify the determinants of fertiliser adoption and rate of application. Although the
158 number of farmers using fertiliser has increased over the years, the rate of application remains well
159 below the recommended amount. The third objective is to measure the impact of the changes in
160 fertiliser use on farm productivity and income. The impact of fertiliser on maize yield is limited
161 when fertiliser is used alone; fertiliser is more effective when used in combination with other
162 technologies such as organic manure, improved maize varieties, integrated pest control, and good
163 agronomic practices (Kibunja et al. 2017). Therefore, in this paper, we attempt to measure the
164 impact of fertiliser use on maize yields in Kenya, controlling for the use of hybrid seed and other
165 factors.

166

167 **2. Material and Methods**

168 **2.1 Sampling Design**

169 The data were collected during rural household surveys conducted in Kenya over the last twenty
170 years: in 1992 (Hassan, Lynam and Okoth 1998); in 2002 (De Groote, Owuor, Doss, Ouma,
171 Muhammad and Danda 2005); in 2010 (De Groote, Narrod, Kimenju, Bett, Scott and Tiongco
172 2016); and in 2013 (Wainaina, Tongrukswattana and Qaim 2016). The first three surveys were
173 cross-sectional, and representative of all the major maize-growing areas of the country, where the
174 large majority of rural households live. All the surveys used a stratified two-stage design, with
175 agroecological zones as strata, sub-locations (the lowest administrative units in Kenya) as primary
176 sampling units, and households as secondary sampling units. During the most recent (2013)
177 survey, the households visited in the third survey were revisited, with a replacement of 20% of the
178 households, randomly selected. Since data were based on repeated cross-sectional surveys and
179 were collected over a long period of time, the same households were not followed over time except
180 in the last survey. The data from the four surveys were previously used to analyse trends in
181 mechanisation in Kenya (De Groote, Marangu and Gitonga 2018).

182 The first survey was conducted in 1992 by the International Maize and Wheat Improvement Centre
183 (CIMMYT) and the Kenya Agricultural Research Institute (KARI) in the major maize
184 agroecological zones of Kenya (Hassan 1998). This survey covered 79 enumeration clusters,
185 randomly selected from the sampling frame of the Central Bureau of Statistics, comprising 1397
186 farmers (Hassan, Lynam and Okoth 1998). The second survey, conducted in 2002, covered 185
187 sub-locations, randomly selected from the 1999 census report (CBS 2001), and 1657 farmers (De
188 Groote et al. 2005). The third survey, in 2010, covered 120 sub-locations, with 1341 farmers (De
189 Groote et al. 2016). The fourth survey (2013) revisited the 2010 sub-locations and the same
190 households except for a replacement of 20% of randomly selected households (Wainaina et al.
191 2016).

192 We follow Hassan's (1998) categorisation of six maize-growing agroecological zones in Kenya.
193 From east to west, these include the coastal lowland tropics, followed by the dry mid-altitude- and

194 dry transitional zones around Machakos. While these zones include 50% of the maize-growing
 195 area, they only produce 30% of Kenyan maize, as they are characterised by relatively low yields
 196 of around 1 t/ha (0.2 to 1.2 t/ha). Further inland, the highland tropics are located in central and
 197 western Kenya, bordered by the moist transitional zones on the east and west. These zones include
 198 30% of the maize-growing area but produce about 50% of Kenya's maize, with comparatively
 199 good yields of over 2.5 t/ha (0.6 to 3.3 t/ha). Finally, the moist mid-altitude zone by Lake Victoria
 200 has moderate yields of 1.5 t/ha (0.4 to 2 t/ha). While Kenya in general has two maize-growing
 201 seasons, the seasons differ in importance between zones. In the highlands, for example, 99% of
 202 maize production takes place in the long rainy season (March-July). In the moist transitional zone,
 203 on the other hand, 49% of the maize is produced in the short rainy season (October-February).

204 In this study, the data from the four surveys were used to describe trends in fertiliser use and maize
 205 yields. We used the panel data of 2010 and 2013 to make a rigorous examination of the
 206 determinants of fertiliser adoption and rate of application. The same panel data set was used to
 207 estimate the impact of fertiliser use on maize productivity and household income. As these two
 208 surveys were conducted in the same households, we were able to examine the changes that
 209 occurred from one period to the other.

210

211 **Table 1: Sample size for the different surveys in the six agroecological zones (AEZ) in Kenya**

AEZ	Year of survey			
	1992	2002	2010	2013
Coastal lowland tropics	99	300	90	89
Dry mid-altitude	177	200	216	216
Dry transitional	78	93	202	203
Moist transitional	412	521	353	355
Highland tropics	448	288	240	238
Moist mid-altitude	183	250	240	239
Total	1397	1652	1341	1340

212

213 **2.2 Analysis**214 **2.2.1 Fertiliser Adoption and Application Rate**

215 Econometric adoption models often use a binary variable as the dependent variable (Maddala
 216 1983); in our study, this is the variable showing whether the household has used fertiliser or not.
 217 The standard models used for panel data analysis are fixed effects and random effects models
 218 (Wooldridge 2002). Compared to the random effects model, the fixed effects model is less
 219 restrictive in assumptions; it does not make the parametric assumption of the distribution of
 220 unobserved heterogeneity, and permits correlation between individual specific effects and
 221 explanatory variables. This allows the fixed effects model to control for time-invariant unmeasured
 222 characteristics of individuals. Since it is based on the time-demeaned data and uses the variation
 223 over time within each cross-sectional observation, explanatory variables that are constant over
 224 time are removed by the time-demeaning and cannot be estimated with the fixed effects model
 225 (Wooldridge 2002) The random effects model, on the other hand, assumes that the error term is
 226 normally distributed, and that the explanatory variables are uncorrelated with the unobserved
 227 heterogeneity, which is a strong assumption. These models use between-household variations to
 228 allow for the estimation of time-variant covariates, but they do not control for time-invariant
 229 individual differences (Greene 2012).

230 To estimate the fertiliser adoption model, random effects logit (RE logit), RE probit and
 231 Chamberlain's correlated random effects (CCRE) probit models were used. In addition, to estimate
 232 the determinants of the fertiliser application rate, we used a hybrid random effects model that
 233 combines the features of both fixed and random effects (Allison 2005). The basic equation of the
 234 hybrid random effects model is given as:

$$235 \quad Y_{it} = \alpha_i + Z_i\gamma + X_{it}\beta_1 + D_{it}\beta_2 + u_{it} \quad (1)$$

236 Where,

237 Y_{it} is the dependent variable for each individual at each time point.

238 i indicates the individual,

239 t denotes the time period,

240 α is the intercept,

241 Z is a vector of time-invariant characteristics,

242 X is a vector of time-varying characteristics,

243 u_{it} is an error term.

244 Given the panel nature of our data, equation 1 can be written in a panel version as (Allison 2005):

$$245 \quad Y_{it} = \alpha_i + Z_i\gamma + X_{it}\beta_1 + D_{it}\beta_2 + (\tau_i + \varepsilon_{it}) \quad (2)$$

246 Where, τ_i is the unobserved heterogeneity term assumed to be individual-specific and time-
 247 invariant and ε_{it} is the random error term. The hybrid approach decomposes the time-varying
 248 independent variables into between-household variation and within-household variation. The
 249 between-household variation is simply the mean of the variable for each individual across time
 250 points and is given by:

$$251 \quad \bar{X} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{i=1}^T X_{it} \quad (3)$$

252 The within-household variation is the difference between each individual's group mean and his or
 253 her variable value at each time point:

$$254 \quad \Delta X_{it} = X_{it} - \bar{X}_i \quad (4)$$

255 Now, the decomposed components are added as predictors in equation 1. The hybrid model can be
 256 specified as follows:

$$257 \quad Y_{it} = \alpha_i + Z_i\gamma + \bar{X}_i\beta_{b1i} + \Delta X_{it}\beta_{w1i} + \bar{D}_i\beta_{b2i} + \Delta D_{it}\beta_{w2i} + u_{it} \quad (5)$$

258 A hybrid approach has two advantages over traditional fixed- and random-effects estimations:
 259 firstly, it provides two interpretations of time-variant explanatory variables – coefficient estimates
 260 for the between-household effects and the within-household effects; secondly, it allows the time-
 261 invariant variables to be included in the model in addition to providing within-household
 262 coefficients identical to the estimates obtained from the fixed effects model.

263 **2.2.2 Impact of Fertiliser Use on Yield and Income**

264 A major criticism of the observational survey data is that they suffer from self-selection bias arising
 265 due to unobservable variables. We used a two-stage endogenous switching regression (ESR) model
 266 (Lokshin and Sajaia 2004) to deal with unobservable bias. The ESR model has been used
 267 extensively to study impact evaluations of agricultural technologies (Jaleta, Kassie, Tesfaye,
 268 Teklewold, Jena and Marennya 2016; Jena 2019; Jena, Stellmacher and Grote 2017; Kassie,
 269 Teklewold, Marennya, Jaleta and Erenstein 2015; Kleemann, Abdulai and Buss 2014; Teklewold,
 270 Kassie, Shiferaw and Köhlin 2013) .

271 The ESR specifies two regimes – the first regime corresponding to the households that adopt the
 272 technology under study, and the second regime comprising the households that do not adopt the
 273 technology – and uses a two-stage estimation process. In the first stage, the selection equation is
 274 estimated as:

275
$$A_i^* = Z_i \alpha + v_i \quad \text{where } A_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } Z_i \alpha + v_i > 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

276 A farmer adopts fertiliser if the expected utility from adoption is higher than the corresponding
 277 utility from non-adoption. Let A_i^* capture the benefit from adopting fertiliser by the i^{th} farmer and
 278 be a latent variable. Z_i is a vector of explanatory variables explaining the selection into the two
 279 regimes, α is the parameter vector, and v_i is the error terms.

280 The second stage estimates the outcome equation. Based on the first stage selection equation,
 281 farmers select themselves to join one of the two regimes. The outcome equations for the two
 282 regimes, i.e. for fertiliser adopters and fertiliser non-adopters, corrected for endogenous adoption
 283 are given as:

284 Regime 1: $Y_{1i} = X_{1i}\beta_1 + \sigma_{1u1i}\hat{\lambda}_{1i} + u_{1i}$ if $A_i = 1$ (Adoption) (2a)

285 Regime 2: $Y_{2i} = X_{2i}\beta_2 + \sigma_{2u2i}\hat{\lambda}_{2i} + u_{2i}$ if $A_i = 0$ (Non-adoption) (2b)

286 where, Y_{1i} and Y_{2i} , $i = 1, \dots, N$, denote the dependent variables in each of the two regimes; X_{1i} and
 287 X_{2i} are the explanatory variables relevant to each regime, β_1 and β_2 are the parameters to be
 288 estimated, and u_{1i} , u_{2i} are the corresponding error terms; $\hat{\lambda}_{1i}$ and $\hat{\lambda}_{2i}$ are the inverse Mill's ratios
 289 (IMR) computed from the first stage selection equation, and are included in equations (2a) and
 290 (2b) to correct for selection bias.

291 The second-stage outcome regressions compute four estimates: (a) the real scenario outcome from
 292 adoption of fertiliser; (b) the real scenario outcome from non-adoption; (c) the counterfactual
 293 outcome scenario from adoption (i.e. the outcome had the adopting households decided not to
 294 adopt) and (d) the counterfactual outcome scenario for non-adoption (i.e. had the non-adopting
 295 households decided to adopt). Situations (a) and (b) are observed from the survey data and hence
 296 are real scenarios, whereas (c) and (d) are hypothetical situations (counterfactual scenarios) that
 297 would be expected to occur if the treated had been untreated, and if the untreated had been treated.
 298 The average treatment effect on the treated (ATT) is computed as (a) - (c) and the average treatment
 299 effect on the untreated (ATU) is computed as (b) - (d).

300

301

302 **3. Results**303 **3.1 Trends of Fertiliser Use and Application Rates in the Pre- and Post-liberalisation Period**

304 Figure 1 shows the proportion of households that used fertiliser over the four survey years. In
 305 1992, the year of the first survey, 62% of farmers used fertiliser. However, the results show
 306 significant inter-regional variations; agroecological zones with good rainfall showed the highest
 307 adoption rates, in particular the moist transitional zone with 80%, and the highland tropics with
 308 57%. Agroecological zones with medium productivity clearly showed lower adoption rates, in
 309 particular the moist mid-altitude zone with 50%, and the dry transitional zone with 40%. The
 310 marginal areas showed low to zero adoption rates: the dry mid-altitude zone had a 12% adoption
 311 rate, and in the lowland tropics, farmers had not applied any fertiliser at all.

312 [Figure 1]

313 Ten years later, in 2002, the average percentage of fertiliser users had increased only slightly, to
 314 65%. The zones with good rainfall – the high tropics and the moist transitional zone – again showed
 315 the highest percentage of fertiliser users, at 89% and 83% respectively. In the medium-potential
 316 areas, the rate of fertiliser adoption was 53% in the dry transitional zone and 33% in the moist mid-
 317 altitude zone, while in the marginal maize areas, the rate was 13% in the lowland tropics and 9%
 318 in the dry mid-altitude zone.

319 The next survey, eight years later in 2010, showed a fertiliser adoption rate of 58%, substantially
 320 lower than the adoption figures in 1992 and 2002. In 2010, the highland tropics and the moist
 321 transitional zones again saw the highest levels of fertiliser adoption, with rates of 77% and 76%
 322 respectively; the dry transitional zone and the moist mid-altitude zone (medium-potential zones)
 323 followed with rates of 58% and 30% respectively; and lastly, the marginal zones of the lowland
 324 tropics and the dry mid-altitude zone had adoption rates of 26% and 16% respectively. Finally,
 325 the 2013 survey, which was a follow-up survey to the 2010 survey, showed an average fertiliser
 326 adoption rate of 65%, a significant increase over 2010, yet not significantly higher than the 1992
 327 and 2002 rates. In the high-potential areas, the high tropics at 87% now registered a significant
 328 improvement in fertiliser adoption, followed by the moist transitional zone at 82%. In the medium-
 329 potential areas, adoption rates were 64% for the dry transitional zone and 48% for the moist mid-

330 altitude zone, while in the low-potential areas, the rates were 24% for the low tropics and 21% for
331 the dry mid-altitude zone.

332 The rates of fertiliser application, expressed in kg per hectare, are presented in Figure 2. The total
333 averages per year were calculated using AEZ population and area weights to ensure
334 representativeness at a national level, following De Groote, Kimenju, Munyua, Palmas, Kassie and
335 Bruce (2020). The seasonally weighted average figures for the four survey years show that the
336 rates of fertiliser application fluctuated. In the first survey in 1992, the application rate was 82 kg
337 per ha; this had increased slightly to 89 kg per ha in 2002. The rate declined substantially, however,
338 to 68 kg per ha in 2010, before eventually rising again to 100 kg per ha in 2013. The high standard
339 deviations for the average figures indicate a high variability in fertiliser application rates between
340 farmers, with a standard deviation higher than the mean in all the years. Such high dispersion
341 suggests heterogeneity in fertiliser application rates in Kenya, which could be influenced by many
342 factors such as availability of fertiliser in the locality, access to credit, level of education, and
343 farmers' willingness to relate fertiliser use to yield and profitability.

344 [Figure 2]

345 Among the six agroecological zones, the variability is also significant over the four survey years.
346 In 1992, the highest application rate was recorded in the high-potential areas: the highland tropics
347 in particular with 109 kg/ha, and the moist mid-altitude zones with 76 kg/ha, followed by the dry
348 transitional areas with 48 kg/ha, the moist transitional zone with 47 kg/ha and the dry mid-altitude
349 zone with 19 kg/ha. A significant increase in application rates can be observed in the lowland
350 tropics, the moist transitional zone and the highland tropics between 1992 and 2002. In that period,
351 there was only a marginal increase in application rates in the dry mid-altitude zone. During the
352 same period, the dry transitional and moist mid-altitude zones experienced a significant decline in
353 application rates.

354 In 2010, the weighted average fertiliser application rate dropped significantly compared to 2002.
355 Among the AEZs, the highest level was again recorded in the highland tropics (113 kg/ha),
356 followed by the moist transitional zone with 102 kg/ha. Application rates in the other zones were
357 substantially less: 38 kg/ha in the dry transitional zone, 27 kg/ha in the moist mid-altitudes, 26

358 kg/ha in the lowland tropics and 6 kg/ha in the dry mid-altitudes. The fertiliser application rates
359 had increased again by 2013, when the highland tropics and moist transitional zones had regained
360 the 2002 levels. The lowland tropics and dry mid-altitude zone also showed higher application
361 rates than in previous years.

362 We observe that there is no clear sign of an increasing or decreasing trend in fertiliser adoption
363 and application rates, as is shown by the fluctuations from year to year; this may be partly due to
364 erratic weather conditions. However, there is a clear indication that fertiliser adoption and
365 application rates were stagnant during the period from 1992 to 2013.

366

367 **3.2 Trends in Maize Yields in Kenya from 1992 to 2013**

368 Next, we analyse the trends in maize yields in Kenya over the same four survey years (Figure 3).
369 Our results indicate that the average maize yield in the country did not increase between 1992 and
370 2013 – a major concern for a country that relies heavily on maize for its food security. The
371 weighted average maize yield was 1360 kg/ha in 1992 but then declined to 1220 kg/ha in 2002; it
372 reached its lowest level in 2010 at 1058 kg/ha before recovering marginally to 1116 kg per ha in
373 2013. Note, however, that the standard errors are between 63 kg/ha (2002) and 125 kg/ha (1992),
374 so the small differences between the survey years are not significant.

375 [Figure 3]

376 To support this finding, we also analysed the FAOSTAT data on maize yields in Kenya from 1961
377 to 2017 (FAO 2019), presented as a solid line in Figure 4, with the average yields from the different
378 surveys indicated as dots (error bars indicate standard errors). The FAO time-series graph shows
379 large year-to-year fluctuations in maize yields, but two trends clearly emerge: firstly, in the period
380 from 1961 to 1990, there was a significant increase in yield ($Y = -50,893^{***} + 27^{***} \times \text{year}$; R^2
381 $= 0.78$). Secondly, in the period since 1990, maize yields have stagnated, with no statistically
382 significant change over time.

383 [Figure 4]

384 Comparing the two data sets presented some difficulty, as the data were collected using different
385 methodologies. The survey data were collected using standard sampling methodology leading to
386 unbiased estimates with an indicator of precision, the standard error. The FAOSTAT data, on the
387 other hand, were not derived from farm surveys, but from estimates by extension and other officers
388 at the local level, basically from expert opinions, which were subsequently aggregated into national
389 figures. As this method is not based on sampling, it does not produce a measure of statistical
390 precision, but it is commonly used because of its low cost. Despite the different methodologies,
391 both estimates show the same trends, although FAOSTAT consistently produces a higher yield
392 estimate, of 476 kg/ha (between 293 and 576 kg/ha) on average.

393 The survey results also show high regional differences, as expected, and these remain high over
394 the 30 years of the study period. The highland tropics recorded the highest maize yields in 1992
395 with 1921 kg per ha, followed by the moist transitional zone with 1722 kg per ha; these are the
396 two zones most suitable for maize production. The other four zones registered significantly lower
397 yields. Nevertheless, yields had increased in the moist mid-altitude zone (812 kg/ha), the dry
398 transitional zone (657 kg/ha) and the dry mid-altitude zone (457 kg/ha). Yields in the lowland
399 tropics remained low and stagnant, between 426 and 547 kg/ha, but with no significant difference
400 over the years. However, the large standard deviations indicate that there is high variation across
401 the farming population in each agroecological zone. This heterogeneity across the country requires
402 rigorous quantitative analysis to identify the specific factors leading to it. Such modelling is
403 presented in the next section.

404

405 **3.3 Fertiliser Adoption and Application by Various Socio-economic Groups**

406 The previous two sections presented fertiliser adoption and application rates across the
407 agroecological zones over the four survey periods. This section classifies adoption and application
408 rates across various socio-economic strata such as gender, prevalence of food insecurity and the
409 seasonally weighted area under maize, using the data pooled over the last two survey years, i.e.
410 2010 and 2013, that are panel surveys. With regard to gender, fertiliser adoption by male-headed
411 households (57%) was on average 6% higher than adoption by female-headed households (51%)

412 (Table 2). Similarly, the fertiliser application rate was 76 kg/ha for male-headed households, but
413 57 kg/ha – 33% lower – for female-headed households. The higher rates of fertiliser adoption and
414 application in male-headed households reinforce the often-argued issue of lack of access to inputs,
415 extension services and credit by female-headed households in comparison to their male
416 counterparts.

417 Secondly, we examine socio-economic groups with respect to their usual food security status, and
418 analyse their fertiliser use according to this criterion. Four categories of food-security prevalence
419 were identified based on the responses to a series of questions (Coates, Swindale and Bilinsky
420 2007): highly food-insecure, moderately food-insecure, mildly food-insecure, and food secure.
421 Food-secure households had the highest rate of fertiliser adoption (70%), while the highly food-
422 insecure group had the lowest (44%). The other groups, mildly food-insecure and moderately food-
423 insecure, had rates of 60% and 53% respectively. Similarly, rates of fertiliser application declined
424 with decreasing food security: from 102 kg/h by the highly food-secure group to 48/ha by the
425 highly food-insecure group.

426 Finally, the third variable that we used to compute fertiliser adoption and application was the
427 seasonally weighted area under maize, again classifying households into four groups: 0 to 1 ha;
428 1.1 to 5 ha; 5.1 to 10 ha; and above 10 ha per household. Among the first three groups, the highest
429 adoption rate, 58%, was found among households with the smallest maize area (0-1 ha); for
430 households with 1.1-5 ha of maize, the adoption rate was 48%, and for households with 5.1-10 ha,
431 it was 55%. The households with the largest maize area (> 10 ha) all used fertiliser, although this
432 group comprised very few households. Similarly, application rates also formed a U-curve in the
433 maize area function: they were higher for the very small areas, at 75 kg (< 1 ha) than in the middle
434 range at 59 kg/ha (1.1-5 ha), and then increased again to 179 (5-10 ha) and 173 kg/ha (> 10ha).

435

436

Table 2: Fertiliser use and quantity used by various socio-economic groups

	% of farmers using fertiliser	Average application rate (kg/ha)	
Sex of household head			
Male	57.2	75.98	(117.42)
Female	51	57.29	(95.90)
Prevalence of food insecurity			
Highly food insecure	43.9	48.29	(91.72)
Moderately food insecure	53.2	57.97	(95.41)
Mildly food insecure	59.9	92.65	(137.64)
Food secure	69.8	101.96	(128.89)
Seasonally weighted maize Area (ha)			
0 – 1 hectare	57.8	74.52	(113.10)
1.1 – 5 hectares	48.1	59.20	(111.34)
5.1 – 10 hectares	55.6	179.18	(193.23)
Above 10 hectares*	100	172.37	(129.82)

437 Source: Own calculation, standard deviation in parenthesis. N for all the categories is 1970.

438

439

440 3.4 Determinants of Fertiliser Use

441 In this section we model the determinants of fertiliser use. The average marginal effects from the
 442 random effects (RE) logit model, RE probit model, and Chamberlain's correlated random effects
 443 (CCRE) probit model are presented in table 3. Both the RE logit and the RE probit models failed
 444 the Mundlak test, implying that the results were not consistent, and therefore we turned to the
 445 CCRE probit model. However, there was consistency among the results from the CCRE and RE
 446 models, except for those for education (formal years of schooling of the household head) and total
 447 area under maize. Both the RE logit and RE probit models showed a positive effect of education
 448 of the household head on fertiliser adoption. The marginal effect was 0.013 (statistically significant
 449 at 1% level of significance). The probability of fertiliser adoption increased by 1.3% for each extra
 450 year of education of the household head. As shown in the CCRE probit model, the seasonally
 451 weighted area under maize also had a positive effect on fertiliser use. An increase in the average
 452 area allocated to maize by 1 ha increased fertiliser adoption by 3%.

453 The agroecological zones were also included in the model, and compared to the lowland tropics
 454 (the base category), farmers in the dry transitional zone, moist transitional zone and highland
 455 tropics were more likely to adopt fertiliser. Weather variables were also included, but only annual
 456 precipitation had a positive but small effect on fertiliser adoption ($p < 10\%$).

457 Among the institutional variables, distance to the nearest agricultural extension office, used as a
 458 proxy for access to extension, was found to have a negative effect on the probability of fertiliser
 459 adoption. The final variable affecting fertiliser adoption was the household food insecurity access
 460 scale (HFIAS)¹. The marginal effect of this was in the range of -0.004 to -0.006, meaning that if
 461 the index value increased by a unit, i.e. if a household became more food insecure, then the
 462 probability of the household using fertiliser decreased by 0.4 to 0.6%. This is in line with the

¹ The HFIAS variable (household food insecurity access scale) used in the regression is a quantitative indicator of food insecurity constructed from the responses to nine occurrence questions that represent a generally increasing level of severity of food insecurity (access) (from "In the past four weeks, did you worry that your household would not have enough food?" to "In the past four weeks, did you or any household member go a whole day and night without eating anything because there was not enough food?"), and nine "frequency-of-occurrence" questions that are asked as a follow-up to each occurrence question to determine how often the condition occurred (Coates et al., 2007).

463 descriptive results in table 5, which show that highly food-insecure households tend to use less
 464 fertiliser.

Table 3: Determinants of fertiliser use

	RE Logit AME	RE Probit AME	CCRE Probit AME
Male head of household	0.00	(0.03) 0.00	(0.03) 0.04 (0.05)
Age of the head of household	0.00	(0.00) 0.00	(0.00) 0.00 (0.00)
Formal years of schooling of the head of household	0.01***	(0.00) 0.01***	(0.00) 0.01 (0.00)
Farming experience of the head of household	-0.00	(0.00) -0.00	(0.00) -0.00 (0.00)
Equivalence based on OECD-modified scale	-0.00	(0.01) -0.00	(0.01) 0.01 (0.01)
Total area under maize(ha) seasonal weights	0.02	(0.01) 0.02	(0.01) 0.03** (0.01)
Dry mid-altitude	-0.12	(0.09) -0.13	(0.09) -0.07 (0.10)
Dry Transitional	0.24*	(0.11) 0.24*	(0.11) 0.29* (0.11)
Moist Transitional	0.36***	(0.10) 0.35***	(0.11) 0.33** (0.11)
High Tropics	0.30*	(0.13) 0.30*	(0.13) 0.29* (0.14)
Moist mid-altitudes	0.05	(0.09) 0.04	(0.09) 0.02 (0.09)
Access to extension services	-0.05	(0.03) -0.05	(0.03) -0.06 (0.03)
Access to credit	0.02	(0.02) 0.02	(0.02) -0.03 (0.04)
Distance to the nearest agricultural extension office (km)	-0.00*	(0.00) -0.00*	(0.00) -0.00* (0.00)
Distance to the village market from residence (walking minutes)	-0.00	(0.00) -0.00	(0.00) -0.00 (0.00)
Household Food Insecurity Access Scale Score	-0.01***	(0.00) -0.01***	(0.00) -0.00* (0.00)
Total precipitation (mm/year)	0.00*	(0.00) 0.00*	(0.00) -0.00* (0.00)
Minimum air temperature, yearly, at 2m height (°C)	-0.01	(0.01) -0.01	(0.01) -0.03 (0.01)
Maximum air temperature, yearly, at 2m height (°C)	0.01	(0.01) 0.01	(0.01) 0.03 (0.02)
Relative humidity (%)	-0.09	(0.23) -0.09	(0.24) 0.4 (0.53)
Year of survey=2013	0.02	(0.02) 0.02	(0.02) 0.02 (0.05)
N	1970	1970	1970

Note: Cluster robust standard errors in parenthesis, *** significant at 1%, ** significant at 5%, * significant at 10%

Means for time-varying variables not displayed for CCRE

465

466 **3.5 Determinants of Fertiliser Application Rate**

467 In this section, we identify the factors that affect the fertiliser application rate, using both the
468 random effects model and Allison’s hybrid model. The random effects model again failed the
469 Mundlak test, hence we focus more on the hybrid model results. The results show that the year
470 dummy is statistically significant and positive, meaning that the application rate in 2013 has
471 increased compared to the application rate in 2010. This finding is corroborated by the statistics in
472 Table 3, which show that the fertiliser application rate has increased in 2013 compared to that in
473 2010.

474 Among the five agroecological zones, the moist transitional zone showed high levels of fertiliser
475 application compared to the base category of the lowland tropics, while the estimated coefficient
476 for the highland tropics was not statistically significant. Furthermore, households who faced
477 greater food insecurity tended to use less fertiliser, as a higher value of the food-insecurity access
478 scale is associated with a reduction in fertiliser application. In addition to the variables discussed,
479 the random effects model has other variables that are statistically significant compared to Allison’s
480 hybrid model, in particular the education of the household head. The results also show an
481 association between education of the household head and fertiliser application rates: each
482 additional year of education is associated with an increase of 3 kg/ha.

483

484

Table 4: Determinants of fertiliser application rate

	RE Model		Allison's Hybrid Model	
Male head of household	4.09	(5.41)	6.95	(10.87)
Age of the head of household	0.22	(0.20)	0.05	(0.46)
Formal years of schooling of the head of household	2.75***	(0.77)	1.60	(1.00)
Farming experience of the head of household	0.21	(0.20)	-0.06	(0.40)
Equivalence based on OECD-modified scale	2.25	(2.00)	-2.81	(3.20)
Total area under maize(ha) seasonal weights	0.16	(2.15)	-3.20	(3.00)
Dry mid-altitude	-20.13	(17.81)	2.53	(21.29)
Dry Transitional	9.04	(20.32)	33.04	(23.05)
Moist Transitional	61.42**	(19.86)	74.59***	(21.74)
High Tropics	30.15	(27.26)	46.56	(28.66)
Moist mid-altitudes	-22.02	(16.30)	-13.45	(18.43)
Access to extension services	2.36	(7.37)	5.11	(40.33)
Access to credit	-1.82	(5.07)	-19.53*	(9.70)
Distance to the nearest agric. ext. office (km)	-0.04	(0.26)	-0.03	(0.32)
Distance to the village market from residence in walking minutes	-0.10	(0.05)	-0.09	(0.08)
Household Food Insecurity Access Scale Score	-1.29***	(0.34)	-0.74	(0.45)
Total annual precipitation (mm)	0.02***	(0.01)	-0.05***	(0.01)
Minimum air temperature, yearly, at 2m height (°C)	1.41	(1.69)	-7.14*	(3.02)
Maximum air temperature, yearly, at 2m height (°C)	-2.96	(1.64)	-2.24	(5.41)
Relative humidity (%)	-33.7	(57.9)	-55.6	(110)
Year of survey=2013	25.05***	(5.65)	3.68	(3.36)
Constant	90.39	(93.83)	-35.48	(111.81)
N	1970		1970	

Note: Standard errors in parenthesis, *** significant at 1%, ** significant at 5%, * significant at 10%

485 4. Impact of Fertiliser Use on Maize Productivity and Household Income

486 Finally, we analyse the effect of fertiliser use on maize productivity and total household income,
487 by using the endogenous switching regression model to calculate the average treatment effect on
488 the treated (ATT) and the average treatment effect on the untreated (ATU) (Table 5). The ATT for
489 maize productivity is 458 kg/ha and significant at 1%, suggesting that households that use fertiliser
490 gain 458 kg/ha compared to the counterfactual scenario in which they do not use fertiliser. The
491 ATU is 87 kg/ha and also statistically significant (at 1%), meaning that households that do not use
492 fertiliser would have gained 87 kg/ha had they chosen to fertilise their maize.

493 Next, we analyse the impact of fertiliser use on the log of total household income (bottom panel
494 of table 5). The ATT is positive (0.06) and statistically significant for log household income,
495 indicating that households that used fertiliser earned more than they would have earned had they
496 not used fertilizer. The ATU for log household income, on the other hand, is not statistically
497 significant, indicating that households that did not use fertiliser would not have obtained a higher
498 total income had they used fertiliser. Because household income also includes income from other
499 sources (although income from maize constitutes the major proportion of household income), it is
500 not surprising that the counterfactual scenario is statistically inconclusive. The ATT, which is a
501 measure of a real scenario, is more important and that has come out as positive. These findings
502 indicate that fertiliser use has a positive impact on both farm productivity and household income,
503 and therefore on household welfare, at least on the adopters.

504

505

506 **Table 5: Average treatment effects of fertiliser use on maize productivity and net total**
 507 **income, ESR Model**

508

Outcome variable	Category	Decision		Adoption Effect
		To use Fertiliser	Not to use fertiliser	
Maize productivity (kg/ha)	ATT	(a) 1461 (19)	(c) 1003 (10)	458 (21)***
	ATU	(d) 787 (22)	(b) 700 (10)	87 (24)***
Log household income (Kenyan Shillings)	ATT	(a) 11.61 (0.02)	(c) 11.55 (0.02)	0.06 (0.03)***
	ATU	(d) 11.19 (0.02)	(b) 11.16 (0.02)	0.27 (0.03)

509 Note: Standard errors in parenthesis; *** significant at 1%, ** significant at 5%, * significant at 10%

510 *ATT =Average Treatment effect on Treated (Fertiliser used);*

511 *ATU=Average Treatment effect on Untreated (Fertiliser not used);*

512 *(a)=adopters with adoption;*

513 *(b)=non-adopters with no-adoption;*

514 *(c)=adopters with no adoption;*

515 *(d)=non-adopters with adoption;*

516

517 Table 6 presents the endogenous switching regression coefficients, indicating the factors that affect
 518 maize yields, for both fertiliser adopters and non-adopters. Education has a negative impact on
 519 maize yields for non-adopters, with a decline of 28 kg/ha for each year of education. This may be
 520 because non-adopters have a lower threshold level of education, such that an increase in education
 521 does not induce any difference in fertiliser application and thus maize yield. Household size (in
 522 adult equivalents), on the other hand, has a positive impact on yield for both adopters and non-
 523 adopters. The use of hybrid maize also positively affects yield for both groups, with an increase of
 524 291 kg/ha for adopters and 174 kg/ha for non-adopters, indicating the synergistic effect of

525 combining both technologies. Maize area per household, in contrast, has a negative and significant
526 coefficient for non-adopters, indicating that a larger maize area leads to a reduction in yield for
527 this group. Among institutional variables, access to extension services has a positive and
528 significant impact, increasing maize yields by 240 kg/ha for fertiliser adopters and 184 kg/ha for
529 non-adopters, indicating a synergy between extension and fertiliser use.

530 Among weather variables, an increase in minimum temperature has a positive effect: for every 1°
531 C, maize yield increases by 78 kg/ha for adopters and 61 kg/ha for non-adopters. However, an
532 increase in maximum temperature decreases yields for non-adopters. Furthermore, annual rainfall
533 has a positive effect on yields for adopters, whereas an increase in relative humidity decreases
534 yields for that group.

535 The ESR results for the log of total household income show significant positive effects of age of
536 the household head and number of adult equivalents on household income for both fertiliser
537 adopters and non-adopters, while the year dummy is found to have a positive effect for non-
538 adopters only. While maize area positively affects household income for adopters, farming
539 experience of the household head has a negative effect. Access to extension services is found to
540 have a positive and statistically significant effect on income for both adopters and non-adopters.
541 Among the AEZ dummies, farmers in the dry transitional, moist transitional, highland tropics and
542 moist mid-altitude zones had less income compared to farmers in the lowland tropics for both
543 adopters and non-adopters. While an increase in minimum temperature increases the average
544 household income for both groups, an increase in maximum temperature reduces it.

545

546

Table 6: Endogenous switching regression on maize productivity

	Fertiliser users		Fertiliser non-users	
Male household head	49.41	(108.93)	-43.75	(62.86)
Age of the head of household	-7.41	(3.98)	-2.09	(2.47)
Formal years of schooling of the head of household	-8.56	(14.21)	-27.96*	(11.07)
Farming experience of the head of household	-1.61	(3.95)	-3.86	(2.16)
Adult equivalent household size	90.87*	(43.25)	55.21*	(26.19)
Total area under maize(ha) seasonal weights	0.39	(32.87)	-122.40***	(28.76)
Dry mid-altitude	-391.41	(343.26)	270.91*	(136.71)
Dry transitional	-1138.60**	(380.89)	-353.69	(193.62)
Moist transitional	-1061.53**	(388.62)	-697.93**	(237.44)
High tropics	-501.97	(458.65)	-371.45	(295.89)
Moist mid-altitudes	-685.85**	(261.59)	-178.35	(151.66)
Access to extension services	240.23*	(110.39)	184.38**	(58.60)
Access to credit	-47.63	(84.99)	-20.08	(53.28)
Distance to the nearest agric. ext. office (km)	9.33	(6.24)	5.57**	(2.15)
Distance to the village market from residence (walking minutes)	-1.62	(1.20)	0.64	(0.66)
Total annual precipitation (mm)	0.17*	(0.07)	0.10	(0.09)
Minimum air temperature at 2m height (yearly minimum) in °C	78.36**	(26.48)	60.88**	(20.08)
Maximum air temperature at 2m height (yearly maximum) in °C	31.78	(24.88)	-65.50**	(21.19)
Relative humidity (%)	-2346*	(970.8)	-208.6	(581.2)
Year of survey=2013	-22.49	(112.08)	-72.59	(56.34)
Hybrid used	290.76**	(110.51)	173.57***	(44.89)
Mills1	-1500.17***	(379.34)		
Mills2			-1128.16***	(286.84)
Constant	3478.48*	(1516.25)	1499.80	(933.25)
N	1103		867	

Note: Robust standard errors in parenthesis, *** significant at 1%, ** significant at 5%, * significant at 10%

Table 7: Endogenous switching regression on log total household income

	Fertiliser users	Fertiliser non-users	
Male household head	0.06	(0.09) 0.15	(0.09)
Age of the household head	0.00*	(0.00) -0.00*	(0.00)
Formal years of schooling of the head of household	0.02	(0.01) -0.01	(0.02)
Farming experience of the head of household	-0.01**	(0.00) -0.00	(0.00)
Equivalence based on OECD-modified scale	0.18***	(0.03) 0.26***	(0.03)
Total area under maize(ha) seasonal weights	0.15***	(0.04) 0.09	(0.05)
Dry mid-altitude	-0.00	(0.33) 0.03	(0.25)
Dry transitional	-1.98***	(0.38) -1.32***	(0.30)
Moist transitional	-2.08***	(0.42) -1.50***	(0.36)
High tropics	-1.85***	(0.46) -1.40**	(0.44)
Moist mid-altitude	-1.03***	(0.27) -0.17	(0.21)
Access to extension services	0.39***	(0.10) 0.69***	(0.11)
Access to credit	-0.02	(0.07) -0.11	(0.07)
Distance to the nearest agricultural extension office (km)	0.01	(0.01) 0.01***	(0.00)
Distance to the village market from residence in walking minutes	0.00*	(0.00) 0.00	(0.00)
Total precipitation (yearly sums) in mm	-0.00***	(0.00) -0.00***	(0.00)
Minimum air temperature at 2m height (yearly minimum) in °C	0.10***	(0.03) 0.07**	(0.02)
Maximum air temperature at 2m height (yearly maximum) in °C	-0.13***	(0.02) -0.08**	(0.02)
Relative humidity (%)	-0.73	(0.82) -0.44	(0.77)
Year of survey=2013	0.17	(0.09) 0.35***	(0.09)
Hybrid used	-0.0	(0.11) 0.13	(0.07)
Mills1	-2.59***	(0.39)	
Mills2		-2.60***	(0.38)
Constant	17.37***	(1.47) 11.52***	(1.31)
N	1102	866	

Note: Robust standard errors in parenthesis, *** significant at 1%, ** significant at 5%, * significant at 10%

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549

550

551 5. Discussion and Concluding Remarks

552 This paper studies the evolution of fertiliser use in the Kenyan maize sector after the agricultural
553 liberalisation policies put in place in the mid-1990s, and the impact of fertiliser use on maize
554 productivity, controlling for other key variables. The present study is unique as it exploits a rich
555 data set collected through four surveys undertaken at different times. The study sets three
556 objectives to contribute to the existing literature: firstly, to analyse the trends in fertiliser adoption
557 and maize yields in Kenya from 1992 to 2013; secondly, to examine the determinants of the
558 adoption and application rates of fertiliser, and, finally, to measure the impact of fertiliser use on
559 maize productivity and household income.

560 The results from the trend analysis show that fertiliser adoption and application rates have been
561 quite volatile over the two decades. When comparing the four time periods, it is apparent that the
562 average uptake of fertiliser adoption in the country has not significantly increased over time.

563 However, these average figures should not hide the wide heterogeneity observed among the AEZs.
564 The two high-potential zones: the highland tropics and the moist transitional zones, have shown
565 high rates of both fertiliser adoption (in % of farmers) and fertiliser application rates (in kg/ha).
566 The other AEZs, in particular the marginal areas of the lowland tropics, moist mid-altitude and dry
567 transitional zones, still lag far behind.

568 Our results are in line with the generally low levels of fertiliser use in sub-Saharan Africa, which
569 are very low compared to Asian and Latin American standards (IFDC 2007). These results,
570 however, contrast with those of other studies, particularly those based on the Tegemeo panel data
571 that show an increase in fertiliser use and maize yields from 1997 to 2007 (Sheahan, Black and
572 Jayne 2013; Olwande, Sikei and Mathenge 2009; Ariga and Jayne 2011). The FAO yield data for
573 this particular period also show an increase in maize yields (Figure 4). However, our analysis,
574 based on both our survey and the FAOSTAT data, indicates that this increase over a short period
575 is not part of a larger trend.

576 The stagnating fertiliser application rates are a matter for grave concern, and it is therefore
577 important to explore possible explanations. Two competing hypotheses try to explain the low rate
578 of fertiliser application in Kenya. Market-based hypotheses suggest that farmers are responding to

579 the high fertiliser prices that are the result of high transportation and marketing costs in Africa
580 (Bumb and Gregory 2006; Jayne, Yamano, Nyoro and Awour 2001), and the resultant low
581 availability of fertilisers and their accessibility to smallholder farmers (Ariga and Jayne 2011).
582 Non-market-based hypotheses emphasise farmers' lack of knowledge about inorganic fertilisers
583 and high yielding varieties, as well as their financial constraints (Morris, Kelly, Kopicki and
584 Byerlee 2007).

585 Our findings cast doubt on the success of the agricultural liberalisation policies. Although private
586 companies are now allowed to operate in the input markets, there is still heavy indirect government
587 control through import policies and domestic distribution policies. Such indirect control inhibits
588 the growth of private participation in providing inputs to farmers. Previous studies have shown
589 that the lack of availability of fertiliser in the market, and limited access to finance are important
590 bottlenecks for farmers (Jena and Odendo, 2014).

591 Nevertheless, our results show that fertilisers have a positive and significant impact on both maize
592 productivity and net total household income of adopters. Moreover, our results show a clear
593 synergistic effect of the use of fertiliser and the cultivation of improved maize varieties: the
594 combined use of these has a clear positive effect on yield.

595 The stagnation of yields of maize, Kenya's major food staple, is worrying. It is also surprising,
596 given the government's efforts in supporting the maize sector. Not only were the control of input
597 provision relaxed and output markets liberalised, paving the way for private investment, but there
598 has also been increased research into agricultural technologies, an enormous growth in financial
599 institutions, and an amazing expansion of mobile phone technology. In view of all these
600 developments, the stagnation of maize yields in Kenya has puzzled policy makers and researchers
601 alike.

602 One probable explanation is that agricultural extension services may not have reached the socially
603 and geographically disadvantaged farmers who live in remote areas away from the location of
604 extension offices. Our findings consistently show that lack of access to extension is a major reason
605 for low adoption rates. Our discussions during focus group discussions (FGDs) and with key
606 extension officers revealed that it is mostly progressive farmers, i.e. those who are socially well-

607 connected and exposed to modern communication methods, who attend extension meetings
608 regularly and take advantage of available technology. A substantial number of farmers who lacked
609 proper communication facilities and a critical level of education could not grasp the benefit of
610 switching to using prescribed levels of fertiliser and other necessary inputs. This in turn prevented
611 them from operating at the forefront of agricultural technological development.

612 Another possible reason for stagnating maize yields in Kenya is a general decline in soil fertility,
613 with the result that the potential benefits of applying fertiliser cannot be fully harnessed. Our study
614 clearly shows that, although large numbers of farmers in Kenya are now using fertiliser, they
615 cannot apply it consistently in the prescribed doses, and the average application has not been
616 increasing. In SSA, one of the main causes of soil nutrient depletion and the resultant low yields
617 is the intensification of land use without the adequate replenishment of lost nutrients (Henao and
618 Baanante 1999); this was confirmed by a recent study in six other SSA countries, which indicated
619 that fallow areas have disappeared, and that the use of organic and chemical fertilisers is too low
620 to maintain soil fertility (Binswanger-Mkhize and Savastano 2017).

621 To increase maize production and yields and to improve food security, the problem of soil fertility
622 should be urgently addressed. Our results indicate that the use of fertiliser is an important practice
623 that increases maize yields for households that have adopted its use.

624 Five important lessons can be drawn for policy formulation. First, because fertiliser
625 recommendation initiatives create awareness and provide information and training, a targeted
626 outreach towards socially and geographically disadvantaged farmers is required. Micro-plans can
627 be developed, especially at smaller administrative levels. This is particularly important given the
628 decentralization in the new constitution, which devolves agricultural extension to the county level.
629 Second, price policies matter: a change in the input/output price ratio can drive changes in fertiliser
630 use. However, while subsidies increase the use of chemical fertiliser, they also lead to a
631 displacement of commercial fertilisers (Sheahan, Black and Jayne 2013; Mather and Jayne 2018).
632 It is therefore important to look at the whole price situation, and to stabilize input as well as output
633 prices. Third, erratic weather conditions and the emergence of diseases and pests such as maize
634 lethal necrosis and fall armyworm negate much of the benefit from investment in inputs, which
635 discourages farmers from consistently adopting the best agricultural practices. Policies need to be

636 considered that incorporate provision for such uncertainties. Shock-prone locations should be
637 identified and preparedness incorporated in the micro-plans. Fourth, more research is clearly
638 required to understand the behavioural bottlenecks that exist among low-adopting farmers, in order
639 to understand their apprehension regarding technology adoption. Finally, while fertiliser is clearly
640 important, it is only one factor in maintaining soil fertility and increasing yield. Our research also
641 indicates that other factors, in particular the cultivation of improved maize varieties, have a
642 synergetic effect with the use of fertiliser. Many other factors also play a role in optimizing the use
643 of fertiliser, although the survey data used did not include information for incorporating these in
644 the analysis. Nevertheless, other studies and analyses have shown that organic matter, soil testing,
645 fertiliser mixtures adjusted to specific soils and crops, integrated pest management, and good
646 agronomic practices can help optimize fertiliser use (Sheahan, Black and Jayne 2013; Vanlauwe
647 and Giller 2006). A holistic approach is therefore needed to better understand the economics of
648 integrated soil-fertility management, in order to guide research and extension in this field that has
649 clear implications for maize production and food security in Kenya.

650

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654 **Conflicts of interest/Competing interests**

655 The authors hereby declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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818 **Fig. 1** Trend in fertiliser adoption rates in Kenya from 1992 to 2013 (in % of farmers adopting)

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820 Source: Own calculation. Standard deviations are in parentheses. The total yearly average was calculated
 821 using AEZ population and area weights to ensure representativeness at a national level following De Groot
 822 et al. (2020).

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824 **Fig. 2** Fertiliser application rate in Kenya between 1992 and 2013 (kg/ha)

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829 **Fig. 3** Average maize yields, by AEZ and year of survey, between 1992 and 2013 (in kg/ha, error
 830 bars are standard errors

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841 **Fig. 4** Comparing trends in household survey data (four years) with FAO statistics for Kenya,
 842 1961 – 2018 (error bars are standard errors).

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